

Supplementary information



(a)



(b)

Figure S1. The EDX results of the 350 °C-annealed samples with and without the 7.5 wt% DMF dose.



(a)



(b)



(c)



(d)

Figure S2. The cross-cut testing results of four samples (a) without the annealing and DMF dose, (b) with 350°C annealing, (c) with preparation of 7.5 wt% DMF dose, and (d) with the 350°C annealing and 7.5 wt% DMF dose.